

Low-Frequency Voltage-Ripple Minimization of Asymmetric Multiport Y-Converter

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Abstract—The asymmetric multiport Y-converter (AY-MPC) offers significant advantages by enabling single-stage power conversion across ports, eliminating bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and high-frequency transformers, and integrating an additional dc port using only a single inductor and two switches. However, achieving balanced ac grid currents and minimizing voltage ripples at the dc ports remains a major challenge. This letter proposes a control approach to mitigate low-frequency voltage ripples in the AY-MPC without requiring additional circuitry—unlike existing state-of-the-art solutions. By reshaping the inductor currents of the extended module to modulate the instantaneous power exchanged with the dc ports and suppress net power fluctuations, the proposed method ensures balanced ac grid currents and minimized low-frequency voltage ripple at the dc ports, while preserving the native AY-MPC structure. Novel current profiles are introduced and evaluated, demonstrating a substantial reduction in voltage ripple and a corresponding decrease in the required capacitance. The converter’s performance is experimentally validated under various operating conditions.

Index Terms—ac-dc power conversion, multiport converter, single-stage converter, three-phase modular converter.

I. INTRODUCTION

Multiport converters (MPCs) have emerged as effective solutions for integrating multiple energy ports into a single hub, providing an alternative to the traditional multi-converter approach [1], [2]. While existing MPC structures mostly rely on either bulky multi-stage intermediate capacitor coupling or complex multi-terminal magnetic element coupling, the multiport Y-converter (Y-MPC) presented in [3] is proposed to overcome the limitations of existing MPC configurations. The Y-MPC enables single-stage power conversion among multiple ports, eliminates bulky intermediate dc-link capacitors and high-frequency transformers, and provides buck-boost capability at all ports. However, it requires an additional six switches and three inductors for each extra dc port, thereby increasing complexity and component count. To address this, the asymmetric multiport Y-converter (AY-MPC), illustrated in Fig. 1, is introduced. The AY-MPC enables the integration of an additional dc port using only a single inductor and two switches, making it a favorable

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solution when the auxiliary port operates at a lower power level than the main port, although it can technically support arbitrary power distributions between port-1 and port-2 [4]. In Fig. 1, the main port-1 supplies V_1 , while the auxiliary port-2 supplies V_2 .

Although the AY-MPC utilizes fewer components than the Y-MPC, resulting in a more compact, cost-effective, and simplified power converter, especially for applications involving dc ports with different power levels, it also presents two significant challenges. The first is maintaining balanced ac grid currents due to its asymmetric structure, and the second is minimizing low-frequency (LF) voltage ripples at the dc ports. The LF voltage ripple on V_2 at the line frequency arises from the single-phase power flow from the ac grid, while V_1 experiences LF voltage ripple due to the unbalanced power transfer from the ac grid to dc port-1 across the three modules as displayed in Fig. 1.

Several techniques have been investigated to minimize LF voltage ripples in ac–dc converters [5]. A common approach involves the use of cascaded conversion stages, implemented either as two-stage or quasi-single-stage topologies [6], [7]. However, this method potentially compromise the overall system efficiency, as both stages process the entire power flow. To address this, compensation circuits that decouple power fluctuation from the dc power path have been proposed and are generally categorized into parallel and series configurations. In parallel compensation, a bidirectional converter—rated for the full dc voltage—operates in conjunction with a buffer capacitor [8]–[10]. In contrast, series compensation inserts a lower-voltage bidirectional converter with a buffer capacitor in series with the dc load [11], [12]. Within the context of MPCs, these techniques require additional hardware at each dc port, such as bidirectional converters and capacitors, which contradicts the MPC objective of achieving a compact, low-component-count interface for multiple ac–dc ports.

Motivated by these limitations, this letter proposes a method to minimize LF voltage ripples in the AY-MPC without introducing additional hardware, thereby preserving the native topology. The approach reshapes the average components of the inductor currents in module a of the AY-MPC, denoted as \bar{i}'_a and \bar{i}''_a , by properly devised current profiles described in this letter. This allows balanced ac grid currents while simultaneously regulating the instantaneous power exchanged between module a and the dc ports to suppress power fluctuations, effectively reducing

Fig. 1: Asymmetric multiport Y-converter (AY-MPC) with typical power flow illustrated.

LF voltage ripples at the dc ports. Consequently, the required capacitance at the dc ports can be reduced while maintaining a limited peak-to-peak voltage ripple. In the following: Sec. II provides a brief analysis of the AY-MPC; Sec. III presents and evaluates three profiles used for shaping the inductors' currents; Sec. IV details the control structure of the AY-MPC; Sec. V showcases the experimental results; and Sec. VI concludes the letter.

II. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION AND ANALYSIS

In the AY-MPC schematic shown in Fig. 1, module *a* consists of two inductors, L_1 and L_2 , and three half-bridges: one on the ac side, labeled S_{0a}/S_{0a} , functioning as a shared buck, and two on the dc sides, labeled S_{1a}/S_{1a} and S_{2a}/S_{2a} , functioning as boost stages. In contrast, modules *b* and *c* each includes a single inductor, L_1 , and two half-bridges $S_{0b,c}/S_{0b,c}$ and $S_{1b,c}/S_{1b,c}$.

The AY-MPC modules are interconnected at a central point, denoted as *m*, which serves as the neutral point for the Y-connection. Since each module operates as a dc-dc converter, it is essential to ensure that the ac-side voltage of each module remains non-negative. Then, an offset voltage V_{off} is introduced between the grid neutral point *n* and *m*, which must be greater than the peak value of the ac grid phase voltage \hat{V}_m . The ac-side voltages v_{xm} are:

$$v_{xm} = v_x + V_{\text{off}} = \hat{V}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x) + V_{\text{off}}, \quad x = (a, b, c) \quad (1)$$

where v_x is the ac grid phase voltages, ω is the ac grid frequency in rad/s, and θ_x is the respective phase angles of v_x , that is $\theta_x = [0, \pm 2\pi/3]$.

Fig. 2: AY-MPC key waveforms, highlighted those of module *a*: (a) voltage and current; (b) duty cycles.

The S_{0x}/S_{0x} and S_{1x}/S_{1x} half-bridges are operated such that only one half-bridge in each module is modulated at any given time, while the S_{2a}/S_{2a} half-bridge is modulated continuously. The duty cycles $\{d_{0x}, d_{1x}, d_{2a}\}^1$ are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} d_{0x} &= \frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_1)}{v_{xm}}, & d_{1x} &= \frac{\min(v_{xm}, V_1)}{V_1}, \\ d_{2a} &= \frac{\min(v_{am}, V_1)}{V_2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

As illustrated in the AY-MPC key waveforms reported in Fig. 2 and considering module *a*, when $v_{am} > V_1$, the S_{0a}/S_{0a} leg is modulated according to d_{0a} , while S_{1a} is turned on and S_{1a} is turned off, clamping the S_{1a}/S_{1a} leg. Conversely, when $v_{am} < V_1$, the S_{1a}/S_{1a} leg is modulated following d_{1a} , while S_{0a} is turned on and S_{0a} is turned off, clamping the S_{0a}/S_{0a} leg. Meanwhile, the S_{2a}/S_{2a} leg is continuously modulated over the entire grid period T based on d_{2a} . Modules *b* and *c* similarly follow the same modulation logic as module *a*.

Disregarding the current through the input filter capacitors C , the input phase currents i_x of modules *b* and *c* are linked to the average inductor current \bar{i}'_x of L_1 via the duty-cycle. The target relationship is given by

$$\bar{i}'_x = \frac{i_x}{d_{0x}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t + \theta_x)}{d_{0x}}. \quad (3)$$

with $x = b, c$, and \hat{I}_m is the peak grid current, such that $P_{ac} = 1.5\hat{V}_m\hat{I}_m = P_1 + P_2$. For module *a*, the L_1 and L_2 inductor currents are summed at the switching node of the S_{0a}/S_{0a} half-bridge leg instead, implying

$$\bar{i}'_a + \bar{i}''_a = \frac{i_a}{d_{0a}} = \frac{\hat{I}_m \sin(\omega t)}{d_{0a}}. \quad (4)$$

¹The duty cycle d_{Nx} of the S_{Nx}/S_{Nx} half-bridge leg of module *x* is defined with respect to the upper switch S_{Nx} , where $N = 0, 1, 2$ and $x = a, b, c$.

Fig. 3: Current references for \bar{i}_a'' to be analyzed for reducing the LF voltage ripples at the dc ports: (a) Y-MPC (6), (b) constant (7), (c) clamped (8). Remarkably, the maximum value in (a) equals the clamped value in (c).

Remarkably, both \bar{i}_a' and \bar{i}_a'' can be freely shaped as long as their sum satisfies (4) to maintain sinusoidal and balanced ac grid currents. This degree of freedom will be utilized in the subsequent analysis to minimize LF voltage ripples at the dc ports by shaping \bar{i}_a'' , and consequently \bar{i}_a' , while satisfying (4). A detailed analysis of the AY-MPC operation is presented in [4].

III. MINIMIZATION OF VOLTAGE RIPPLES AT THE DC PORTS

A. Proposed current profile

Assuming ripple-free dc current at dc port-2, denoted as I_2 , the resulting \bar{i}_a'' is calculated as

$$\bar{i}_a'' = \frac{I_2}{d_{2a}}. \quad (5)$$

As d_{2a} tends to zero when v_{am} approaches its minimum value (i.e., $V_{off} - \hat{V}_m$), the semiconductor devices and inductors of module a are subject to excessive current stresses. Therefore, LF voltage ripple cancellation does not present a viable solution. Instead, three different current profiles are analyzed for \bar{i}_a'' to minimize the voltage ripples without significantly increasing the current stresses on the AY-MPC components. The \bar{i}_a'' references are presented in Fig. 3 and described below:

a) Y-MPC reference: The inductor currents are imposed as done in [3], distributing the i_a current among L_1 and L_2 proportionally to the power associated with the output dc port. In particular, starting from (4), the average L_2 inductor currents is set to

$$\bar{i}_a'' = \frac{2P_2}{\hat{V}_m d_{0a}} \sin(\omega t). \quad (6)$$

b) Constant reference: The inductor current \bar{i}_a'' is controlled to be constant, which magnitude is controlled to deliver the required P_2 , that is

$$\bar{i}_a'' = \frac{I_2}{d_{2a}^{avg}} = \frac{P_2}{V_2 d_{2a}^{avg}}, \quad (7)$$

with d_{2a}^{avg} the average value of $d_{2a}(t)$ in the grid period. This dc waveform minimizes current stresses on port-2 components while also reducing the LF voltage ripples.

Fig. 4: Main waveforms for different \bar{i}_a'' profiles: (a) Y-MPC (6), (b) constant (7), and (c) clamped (8). Instantaneous power transferred from module a to port-2 is $\bar{p}_2 = d_{2a} \bar{i}_a'' V_2$, while instantaneous power transferred from each module to port-1 is $\bar{p}_{1x} = d_{1x} \bar{i}_a' V_1$. The waveforms illustrate how the current profiles reshape \bar{p}_{1a} and \bar{p}_2 , while \bar{p}_{1b} and \bar{p}_{1c} keep the same, resulting in reduced power fluctuations at the dc ports in case (b) and (c). The shaded areas in the \bar{i}_{C1} and \bar{i}_{C2} waveforms represent the stored charge in $3C_1$ and C_2 , respectively, under the different current profiles.

c) Clamped reference: The \bar{i}_a'' reference current is obtained from (5), which ideally removes voltage ripples, with its value being upper-clamped to the peak value of the Y-MPC reference in (6). The \bar{i}_a'' is defined as

$$\bar{i}_a'' = \min \left(\frac{2P_2}{\hat{V}_m d_{0a}^{min}}, \frac{I_2}{d_{2a}} \right), \quad (8)$$

where d_{0a}^{min} is the minimum value of $d_{0a}(t)$ in the grid period.

The three \bar{i}_a'' profiles, along with their corresponding \bar{i}_a' counterparts that ensure sinusoidal and balanced ac grid currents in accordance with (4), are illustrated in Fig. 4. Here, V_1 and V_2 are set at 400 V and 500 V, respectively, while P_1 and P_2 are set at 3 kW and 1 kW, respectively. To evaluate the influence of these current profiles on the instantaneous power flow, Fig. 4 also presents the instantaneous power delivered from module a to port-2, denoted \bar{p}_2 , and the power delivered from each module to port-1, denoted \bar{p}_{1a} , \bar{p}_{1b} , and \bar{p}_{1c} . Their total contribution, \bar{p}_1 , is also shown. The results highlight that \bar{p}_2 exhibits significantly reduced fluctuations when using clamped or constant current

Fig. 5: Required C_{dc} for the three \bar{i}_a'' waveforms with $V_1 = 400$ V and $P_1 = 3$ kW: (a) across different V_2 values with $P_2 = 1$ kW; and (b) across different P_2 values with $V_2 = 500$ V. The required capacitance for the constant and clamped waveforms is approximately 18% and 36% of that required for the Y-MPC waveform, respectively.

Fig. 6: Comparison of current stresses on module a 's dc-side switches and inductor currents under different current profiles.

profiles compared to the Y-MPC reference. Similarly, variations in \bar{p}_{1a} under different current profiles are clearly visible, whereas \bar{p}_{1b} and \bar{p}_{1c} remain unaffected. As a result, \bar{p}_1 shows reduced fluctuations when clamped or constant waveforms are applied.

Additionally, the average capacitor currents for port-1 and port-2, denoted as \bar{i}_{C1} and \bar{i}_{C2} , are plotted to highlight the energy storage behavior in the system. As shown in Fig. 4, the constant and clamped \bar{i}_a'' waveforms lead to a substantial reduction in the stored charge compared to the Y-MPC reference. This translates into a lower capacitance requirement for the same ripple specification. Notably, the stored energy is balanced between port 1 and port 2, resulting in an equal required dc-link capacitance C_{dc} , where $C_{dc} = 3C_1 = C_2$. The total stored charge ΔQ , along with C_{dc} , are determined by

$$\Delta Q = \left| \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \bar{i}_{C2} dt \right| = \left| \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (d_{2a} \bar{i}_a'' - I_2) dt \right|, \quad C_{dc} = \frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta V}. \quad (9)$$

where ΔV is the peak-to-peak voltage ripple at the dc ports.

B. Evaluation of current profiles

To further illustrate the impact of the three \bar{i}_a'' profiles, Fig. 5a shows the required C_{dc} to achieve $\Delta V = 10$ V as V_2 varies from 450 V to 800 V, with $V_1 = 400$ V, $P_1 = 3$ kW, and $P_2 = 1$ kW. The results demonstrate that the needed C_{dc} for the constant and clamped profiles presents 18% and 36%, respectively, of the C_{dc}

Fig. 7: Control structure of the AY-MPC: (a) The overall block diagram highlighting the main control loops and current profiles generation; A detailed description of: (b) S_{0x}/S_{0x} modulators; (c) S_{1x}/S_{1x} modulators; and (d) S_{2a}/S_{2a} modulator.

needed for the Y-MPC profile. For instance, at $V_2 = 500$ V, the corresponding C_{dc} values are 2.86 mF, 1.04 mF, and 0.51 mF for the Y-MPC, constant, and clamped waveforms, respectively. Fig. 5b further illustrates the linear increase of C_{dc} with P_2 for the current profiles. This trend indicates that operating the AY-MPC at high P_2 levels is less favorable, as it necessitates a larger capacitance. On the other hand, the value of P_1 does not influence ΔV and can therefore be increased without compromising the converter's performance.

The \bar{i}_a'' current profiles directly affect the current stresses on module a dc-side switches ($S_{1a}, S_{1a}, S_{2a}, S_{2a}$), whose corresponding currents are $i_{1a}, i_{1a}, i_{2a}, i_{2a}$, respectively. They also influence the inductor currents i_a' and i_a'' . The current stresses of the remaining components are unaffected by the profile selection. Fig. 6 compares the current stresses associated with the different profiles. The clamped waveform results in the highest stress levels for most components, except for i_{2a} . The constant waveform achieves the lowest stresses for port-2 switches, although it incurs higher stresses on port-1 switches compared to the Y-MPC case. Overall, while the clamped waveform enables the greatest reduction in C_{dc} , it does so at the cost of increased current stress. The constant waveform provides a more balanced compromise, significantly reducing C_{dc} with minimized port-2 current stress.

IV. CONTROL AND MODULATION

The control structure of the AY-MPC, illustrated in Fig. 7a, consists of two outer voltage control loops, each paired with a corresponding inner current control loop. The first loop regulates

Fig. 8: Experimental waveforms of the AY-MPC with $V_{dc1} = 400$ V and $V_{dc2} = 500$ V at different i_a'' current modulation strategies. Steady-state results at $P_{dc1} = 3$ kW and $P_{dc2} = 1$ kW: (a) Y-MPC; (b) constant; (c) clamped. Transient behavior when P_1 is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW with P_2 constant at 0.5 kW: (d) Y-MPC; (e) constant; (f) clamped. Transient behavior when P_2 is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW with P_1 constant at 3 kW: (g) Y-MPC; (h) constant; (i) clamped.

V_1 and i_x , while the second loop controls V_2 and i_a'' to impose the proposed current profiles. The voltage V_1 is regulated to follow a reference V_1^* using a proportional–integral (PI) controller, which sets the reference peak grid current \hat{I}_m^* . This current reference \hat{I}_m^* is fed into a phase-locked loop (PLL) synchronization stage to generate the reference grid currents i_x^* , $x = (a, b, c)$, for the inner current control loop. The actual grid currents i_x are estimated from inductor current measurements and the reference duty cycles d_{0x}^* , as defined by (3) and (4). The error between i_x^* and i_x is transformed from the abc frame to the $\alpha\beta$ frame and processed by a proportional–integral–resonant (PIR) controller. The controller's output is then transformed back to the abc frame and fed to the S_{0x}/S_{0x} and S_{1x}/S_{1x} modulators, which are detailed in Fig. 7b and Fig. 7c, respectively.

Similarly, the second loop regulates V_2 to follow a reference

V_2^* using a PI controller, which generates the reference for the L_2 current $i_a''^*$ based on the selected current profile. For the Y-MPC reference, the controller output is synchronized with v_a and divided by d_{0a}^* , as defined in (6). For the constant reference, the controller output is directly applied to the inner current controller. In the case of the clamped reference, the controller output is divided by d_{2a}^* and saturated to a peak value equal to the Y-MPC peak value, according to (8). The error between $i_a''^*$ and i_a'' is then processed by a PI controller, whose output is directed to the S_{2a}/S_{2a} modulators, as detailed in Fig. 7d.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The AY-MPC prototype combines four half-bridge power modules Imperix PEB8024, utilizing C2M0080120D SiC MOSFETs for the dc-side half-bridges. The ac-side half-bridges use

Fig. 9: Experimental waveforms of V_1 and V_2 at $P_1 = 3$ kW and $P_2 = 1$ kW highlighting the LF voltage ripple for different \bar{i}_a'' current profiles: (a) Y-MPC; (b) constant; and (c) clamped.

UF4SC120023K4S SiC MOSFETs, which feature a lower on-state resistance compared to the dc-side devices. The inductors L_1 and L_2 are 330 μH units, while a single-stage input filter is used with $L_f = 1.2$ mH and $C_f = 10$ μF . Each Imperix half-bridge includes a dc-link capacitor of 235 μF ; therefore, the total capacitance is $3C_1 = 705$ μF and $C_2 = 235$ μF .

Experimental waveforms of the AY-MPC prototype operating in steady-state, with $V_1 = 400$ V, $V_2 = 500$ V, $P_1 = 3$ kW, $P_2 = 1$ kW, using the original Y-MPC, constant, and clamped \bar{i}_a'' waveforms, are presented in Fig. 8a, Fig. 8b, and Fig. 8c, respectively. Despite the asymmetric structure, the ac grid currents remain balanced and well-synchronized with the ac voltages independently of the selected \bar{i}_a'' reference.

The transient behavior when P_1 is increased from 1 kW to 3 kW, with $P_2 = 0.5$ kW, is illustrated in Fig. 8d, Fig. 8e, and Fig. 8f for the Y-MPC, constant, and clamped \bar{i}_a'' waveforms, respectively. In all cases, the system exhibits smooth and stable transitions. Notably, the i_a'' waveform remains unchanged throughout the transient, highlighting effective power decoupling between P_1 and P_2 .

Similarly, Fig. 8g, Fig. 8h, and Fig. 8i present the main waveforms when P_2 is increased from 0.1 kW to 1 kW, with $P_1 = 3$ kW, again for the Y-MPC, constant, and clamped profiles, respectively. These results confirm the stable and seamless dynamic behavior under varying P_2 . During this transient, the variation in i_a'' reflects the controller's action to maintain balanced ac grid currents. It is worth noting that P_1 remains constant and is not affected by the step change in P_2 . Although i_a'' varies due to the change in i_a'' , modules b and c are regulated accordingly to compensate and preserve balanced grid currents.

Fig. 9 presents the experimental waveforms of V_1 and V_2 at $P_1 = 3$ kW and $P_2 = 1$ kW, highlighting the LF voltage ripple for different \bar{i}_a'' current profiles. The results demonstrate a significant reduction in LF voltage ripples with the proposed current profiles, with the clamped waveform achieving a reduction of over 80% and the dc waveform achieving a reduction of over

62% compared to the original waveform.

Efficiency measurements of the AY-MPC prototype were conducted, with P_1 swept from 0.3 kW to 3 kW in 0.1 kW steps and P_2 from 0.25 kW to 1 kW in 0.05 kW steps. Peak efficiencies of 95.36%, 95.29%, and 94.88% were recorded for the Y-MPC, constant, and clamped profiles, respectively, with average power losses across the entire range of 119.1 W, 123.6 W, and 153.8 W. While the prototype is not optimized for each profile, only a minimal increase in loss is observed for the constant profile compared to the Y-MPC, whereas higher losses in the clamped profile are mainly due to increased current stress on module a dc-side devices. Selecting devices with higher current ratings is expected to reduce the disparity in power losses among the different current profiles.

VI. CONCLUSION

This letter presents a technique for minimizing LF voltage ripples in the AY-MPC. Unlike conventional methods—which typically require additional circuitry, such as bidirectional converters and buffer capacitors for each dc port—the proposed approach relies solely on reshaping the inductor currents of the extended module to regulate instantaneous power flow to the dc ports, without any hardware modifications. Novel current profiles, namely Y-MPC, constant, and clamped, are introduced and evaluated. Among these, the constant and clamped profiles demonstrate a substantial reduction in LF voltage ripples and the required C_{dc} compared to the Y-MPC. Moreover, the observed linear increase of C_{dc} with P_2 suggests that operating the AY-MPC at low P_2 levels is favorable, whereas the value of P_1 does not influence C_{dc} and can thus be increased without compromising the converter's performance. Experimental results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed method under various operating conditions. Future research will focus on the optimal design of the AY-MPC tailored to each current profile.

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